

Migration and Its Consequences

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ABSTRACT: Migration, as a social phenomenon, has an especially complex character and can be analyzed from the point of view of the state which is the source of the migration as well as from the point of view of the state which is the destination of the migration. Its causes are especially complex but the economic ones are determinant and are fundamentally different of the causes which determine the population to seek refuge in case of armed conflict. The effects of the migration are equally complex and can be analyzed from the point of view of the source states as well as from the point of view of the destination states. This study conducts an applied analysis of the phenomenon regarding a territorial and administrative division from Romania.

KEY WORDS: migration, immigration, emigration, refugee, exodus, causes, consequences, Brexit.

An extraordinary complex phenomenon it has become nowadays an extremely important problem which affects family, the local and international community as well as the states.

If during the communist regime in Romania one could talk about an internal migration, namely of the people from villages towards cities as a consequence of Romania's forced industrialization, an uprooting caused by political and economical factors, nowadays the phenomenon have become so complex and multi-valent that it covers a lot of field approaches.

Thus, the transition from a centralized economy and forced industrialization to a new society based on decentralization and

private property, from a social organization and pyramidal politics to an organization specific to the market economy has led, in consequence, to unprecedented demographic, economic and social movements in Romania's modern history. The fast impoverishment of the population, the lack of capitalist and neoliberal type of education, the mentalities inherited from the previous age which focused on the concept of the all powerful state and stability have created the objective conditions of triggering this migration phenomenon which has consequences no one even dreamed about only a short while ago.

In Romania's case it produced a strong depopulation of the urban communities, especially of the rural ones leading to the rapid aging of the local population amidst the fast and constant demographic decline. The active population migrated massively, especially the young work force but also the highly qualified one (e.g. IT specialists, doctors, architects, researchers, etc). This phenomenon has consequently brought with itself a social and demographic setback. The main causes being the economic and existential ones, however one cannot neglect the other types of causes such as: lack of a professional future, lack of interest from the decision makers, the will to affirm oneself, etc.

The consequences of this phenomenon are extremely complex. Thus on one hand it precisely solves certain existential requests of those who migrate due to economic issues and implicitly offer financial support to those who stayed at home and indirectly to the Romanian state. On the other hand the family relations are irreversibly destroyed by the forced separation of the spouses, of parents and children, of the old people and the young who left, etc. Then the integration of those who left in other moral values, cultural, religious and economic systems is very difficult even more so for the elderly. Social and familial dramas multiply and grow in geometrical progression reaching worrisome proportions. We thus notice on one hand more depressions and mental illnesses for the children who are left alone at home with their grandparents, grand-grandparents or close relatives and on the other the elderly abandonment by the young which completely destroys the patriarchal concept of the

Romanian, Balkan and Eastern family in which the grandparents, the children and the grandchildren lived together in harmony.

Migration coupled by the demographic decline constitutes for Romania one of the greatest dangers even for the national security.

On the other hand migration constitutes a deep and important concern for the host countries of this phenomenon. Thus the high number of migrants creates distortions on the local work market force. Even if this phenomenon does bring certain benefits for the host countries, such as economic growth, the overwhelming of the local population by the economic migrants causes a reaction of rejection towards them. If the phenomenon would be scarce and took a long time then the assimilation of the migrants by the local population would have been much more efficient and without collateral consequences. If the economic migration overlaps with the refugee crisis from areas with armed conflicts then we can talk about a real phenomenon which had the Biblical Exodus as a precedent in history. We are talking about the massive relocations of people due to the war in Syria, the millions of refugees in Turkey, the hundreds of thousands in Europe who entered through Greece and Italy, etc. The European Union tried countless times to solve this situation either by implementing obligatory quotas for the member states by the J.A.I. Council, or stopping the breaches at the external borders of Europe, or through agreements with Turkey to keep them on its territory. However it is believed that 'stopping at the source' of the phenomenon is the best way which consists in stopping the war in Syria, helping this country to rebuild after the war and returning its scattered population home. We are talking about a multitude of action plans but the only sure things are the consequences and 'calming the refugee's effects' only represents a temporary fix which does not solve the situation. The EU member states reaction to the obligatory quotas is well known and ranges from total rejection to even leaving the EU. The result of the recent referendum in the United Kingdom regarding the Brexit was determined first of all by the rejection of immigration by this state. The consequences are still unknown and only time will be able to answer the questions that derive from this phenomenon.

Hence migration has long surpassed being addressed only casuistic and in theory making an abrupt entry into the practical and existential sphere of the world's nations and states. At the moment it is one of the phenomena which preoccupy the public opinion most because its effects lead to the deepest existential corners of the human being. We can draw from this never ending dissertations and academic analysis that a 'roman fleuve' would be unable to exhaustively address this problem. An exhaustive analysis of the emigration phenomenon in the current context of the development of civilizations being impossible we propose to catch certain punctual aspects which affect the economic and social life of a county in Romania for which we can make some ascertainments related to the extremely vast topic of migration.

Thus, having as an object of study the Dâmbovița County, we can make certain observations regarding the migration phenomenon.

A longitudinal analysis, in time, having as an object of focus the modern, contemporary, development period of this county I noticed an interesting fluctuation regarding migration.

If prior to 1968, when this area belonged to a larger region and there was no county division of the country, it was a certain lull regarding emigration the population was somewhat stable and the forced industrialization wasn't as stressed. After the county was formed began the massive industrialization of this territory so the population from the country migrated towards the cities and the commute phenomenon was in full swing at the time. Besides the country to cities migration it was also felt the migration from the less industrialized areas of the country towards the more developed ones, and the Dâmbovița County, being a developed area, attracted a lot of work force from other geographical areas of the country. The availability of jobs, the social politics regarding commuting, education, healthcare, made possible this migration without visible negative effects towards the population. It was actually an internal migration, between the same national borders where the cultural and religion impact wasn't significant. Meanwhile the population homogenized and the eventual negative effects of the migration became blurred therefore we cannot discuss about special consequences of the phenomenon.

The Revolution from 1989 completely shifted the paradigm of migration because it led to a total turnover of the value system starting from the base towards the superstructure.

The step by step destruction of the national economy branches, the ineptitude or the lack of economic development strategies of the country, the adaptation of the old mentalities to the new social, political and economic realities resulted pretty fast in the emphasis of the migration phenomenon leading today to severe and even irreversible consequences. With the opening of the national borders and the negotiations regarding our country's integration into the European and Euro-Atlantic organizations, in the previously mentioned context, began the massive depopulation of the county. If in 1990 the county's population was approximately 545.000 people in 2011, at the last census we barely reached 505.000 people. Migration combined with the regressive demographic phenomenon, in the context mentioned above, led to this massive depopulation of the county. In 2007, in Castelion, Spain, alone there were 20.000 people from the Dâmbovița County. This migration led on short term to getting some jobs abroad for those who left and a pretty fragile economic 'stability' of the county. Those working abroad send money to those at home and with that money almost all of them would build houses and buy cars (the Romanian dream from the communist era!). This led not only to choking the traffic in the county's towns but also to environment pollution due to uncontrolled tree cuttings. The irreversible destruction of the economic branches caused the county to transform from a heavy industrialized county into a modest one without a consistent and multilateral industry. Commerce grew unchecked, the rail transport took such a dramatic plunge that some railways came close to being closed with others shutting down permanently (note the industrial lines or even the civilian ones such as the railroad connecting the town of Moreni to the rest of the county!)

Beyond the economic aspects mentioned above, the social, moral and cultural ones are dramatic. The number of divorces grew exponentially through attacking the families separated by the flux of the economic migration. The number of births lowered, the number of deaths grew and the social phenomena diversified and amplified.

Thus the number of children left in the care of their grandparents or close relatives grew a lot and depression and mental illness among children and your people became alarmingly high. Moreover the villages in the county are old and the elderly people left without the support of their children who went abroad to work, find themselves into an unprecedented existential helplessness.

In this dramatic context the local and county authorities find themselves in the position of solving an unprecedented situation so their decisions are sometimes ungainly and inefficient. Thus they try to attract foreign investments and several remarkable steps have already been achieved for this successfully privatizing the Special Steels Enterprise from Târgoviște and the Fridge Factory from Gănești by bringing the Renault Technologic Centre to Titu, and creating industrial parks so that in the last few years the local migration phenomenon slowed down a bit because of that. On the other hand a lot of people from the county who are working abroad plan on coming back when they retire so they invest in small family business to assure them a certain existential comfort. Moreover it was tried in Castelion, for example, until the Romanian state formed a consulate in that town, to form a county representative to serve as a gathering place for those abroad, a centre for documentation and enlightenment as well as an office to resolve certain marital status issues. More so, even the church got involved by financing and orthodox church in Castelion where those who ended up on these lands can satisfy their spiritual need according to the cultural and moral Romanian tradition.

We don't know what the future holds, but the issues mentioned above are far from being resolved. We hope for a reflux of those who migrated abroad. For this the economic policies for attracting the work force will continue and will be on the agenda of the local public authorities. On the other hand the national mental collective as well as the dâmbovițean one rejects the very idea of receiving on our territory the refugees that are to be relocated to Romania. Perhaps it is a paradox for a people that knows the migration phenomenon rejects the idea of receiving other nationalities on its territory, however the media coverage of the bomb attacks, the savagery of terrorism, the religious and spiritual gap between Romanians and

Muslims lead to such concussions. The Romania people's tolerance is well known, the peaceful living together in Dobrogea between Romanians, Turks and Tatars is already a good example, however the acceptance of the obligatory quota is heavily rejected. Speaking about good manners and tolerance. The fact that the Romanian orthodox people voted for president a German ethnic by evangelical faith says a lot! Such examples can be multiplied and prove the aforementioned assertion.

In conclusion migration is and will continue to be a long while from now a complex problem. Right now it even affects the national security and the public policies to stop or diminish the phenomenon are not quite strong enough to lead to a massive reversibility of the phenomenon.